

Multi-Objective Optimization Approach for Optimizing the Performance of Double-Stage and Lapple Cyclone Separator

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(Received January 23, 2025; Revised April 21, 2025; Accepted May 02, 2025)

Abstract: Cyclone separators play a crucial role in various industrial applications, particularly in particle filtration for environmental and health protection. This study employed Response Surface Methodology (RSM), Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Multi Objective Genetic Algorithm (MOGA), and a novel approach called Multi Objective for Ant Lion optimizer (MOALO) to optimize the performance of double-stage and lapple cyclone separators. Through statistical analysis, this study investigates the impacts of cyclone diameter, inlet velocity, and size of the particle on the total efficiency, grade removal efficiency, and pressure drop. The results indicate that the double-stage cyclone separator is preferable to the lapple cyclone separator. The RSM and ANN models exhibit high predictive accuracy, with R² values indicating strong correlations with actual data. Optimal operating conditions for the double cyclone have been identified with the cyclone diameter 400 mm, inlet velocity 12 m/s, and particle size 1.68 μm , resulting total efficiency of 80.58%, pressure drop of 689.71 Pa, and grade removal efficiency of 61.59%, providing insights for improving cyclone separator performance. This research highlights the effectiveness of RSM, ANN, MOGA and MOALO in optimizing cyclone separators.

Keywords: artificial neural network; cyclone separator; MOGA; MOALO; response surface methodology

1. Introduction

Cyclone separators are essential in chemical processing and environmental cleansing, and they are highly regarded among various types of engineering equipment¹. Cyclone separator used to separate particles in various industrial settings, as well as both indoor and outdoor situations². Particle filtration is a widely used method in several industries, such as chemical operations, oil refining, petrochemical goods, pharmaceuticals, agriculture, and mineral extraction. Its purpose is to protect the environment and public health by removing dangerous particles from an air stream³.

Several studies have been carried out to enhance the performance of cyclone separator. These efforts have focused on optimizing design by exploring novel configurations to achieve better separation performance. The integration of multiple cyclones in series has attracted attention as a strategy to bolster separation performance and heighten collection efficiency through multi-stage separation⁴. Zhao et al.⁴ introduced new cyclone configuration by connecting two cyclones in a small-scale detached vessel unit to produce a two-stage of separation process. In this model, the discharge of the initial cyclone

is closely linked to the inlet of the subsequent cyclone. This connection can significantly enhance the effectiveness of particle collection. Similarly, Zhu et al.⁵ proposed a compact cyclone cylinder within the primary cyclone cylinder to achieve several rotating separations within a single unit. The presence of an extra vortex intensified the centrifugal force, resulting in an extended retention time for particles and consequently increasing the collection efficiency. Moreover, Xiang and Lee⁶ developed three connection stages to analyse and compare the performance of the double cyclone and conventional cyclone separator.

On the other hand, several studies also have extensively examined the complexities of optimizing the performance of cyclone separators by investigating the geometric elements that impact their efficiency^{7, 8}, analysing the influence of modification and additional part of cyclone separator such as the diameter of the vortex finder⁹, inlet configuration¹⁰, modifications to the dust collector configuration¹¹, and innovative changes to the cyclone separator such as the addition of water nozzles¹², and insertion of a repds¹³. The implementation includes the incorporation of a new type of cyclone, specifically a slit-cyclone cyclone¹⁴, additional inlets¹⁵, a finned cylinder

body¹⁶). Furthermore, additional extra top for the inlets¹⁷, additional for liquid jets¹⁸, a stabilizer at the cylinder¹⁹, a tangent chamber²⁰, a vane with spiral guide²¹, and a concave shape²²). Although significant efforts have been conducted, most of them focus on developing configurations, investigating geometries, and adding cyclone separator parts to enhance performance of the cyclone separator. However, they did not simultaneously enhance overall performance of the cyclone separator, particularly for a novel design used for higher efficiency and minimum pressure drop.

To address this issue, Response Surface Methodology (RSM) is widely used for uncovering complex relationships between design variables and performance criteria in cyclone separators. In addition to RSM, Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) have also attracted significant research attention in understanding and enhancing cyclone separator performance²³). RSM is used to forecast the performance results of the separator in relation to its efficiency and the reduction in pressure drop²⁴) and ANN is used to practical solutions to various problems by simplifying the complex task of identifying correlations between experimental variables²⁵). Qiao et al.²⁶) Indicate that RSM is used to identify the most favourable operational conditions of the separator. Elsayed and Lacor²⁷) reduced the pressure drop by employing a response surface technique model and artificial neural network to accurately represent the interaction effects among the design elements. Safikhani²⁸) used ANN modeling to perform a multi-objective optimization analysis on Karagoz cyclones to improve their collection efficiency and minimize pressure loss. Brar and Elsayed²⁹) also used ANN to perform multi-objective optimization with three response to obtain optimum design results in better performance for the cyclone separator. However, the algorithmic advantages of ANN have not received sufficient attention in the context of performance evaluation for cyclone separators³⁰).

Despite numerous studies conducted at improving cyclone separator performance through geometric modifications and additional components, a significant research gap remains in the application of multi-objective optimization techniques. Existing literature predominantly focuses on single-objective optimization, failing to consider grade removal efficiency as a factor affecting cyclone performance. Additionally, there has been no multi-objective optimization of novel double-stage cyclone separators, overlooking the potential benefits of approaches such as RSM, ANN, MOALO, and MOGA in simultaneously optimizing efficiency, pressure drop, and grade removal efficiency. This gap underscores the need for further exploration, particularly in optimizing both single and double cyclone separators. The significance of multi-objective optimization lies in its capacity to concurrently evaluate and balance multiple performance

criteria, thereby identifying trade-offs and interactions between different objectives.

The purpose of this paper is to optimize lapple and double-stage cyclone separators using RSM, ANN, MOGA, and the newly developed MOALO. MOGA is a type of evolutionary optimization technique that has been effectively employed in previous studies^{31,32}) for optimizing the geometry of cyclone separators. In this study, MOALO represents a novel approach to optimize lapple and double-stage cyclone separators. A Multi-objective Ant Lion Optimizer (MOALO) is a type of optimization technique used to solve engineering problems³³). The experimental data results used in this study are based on influential research conducted by Guoyin Yu et al.³⁴). This study fills a significant gap by leveraging RSM, ANN, MOGA, and MOALO techniques to optimize lapple and double-stage cyclone separators, aiming to enhance their performance for high efficiency, low pressure drops, and high-grade removal efficiency.

2. Model and Methodology

This study aims to optimize the performance of the cyclone with lapple-type before and after the addition of the pre-separation outer of the cyclone separators. To do this, newly built a double-stage and lapple cyclone separators were selected for analysis and clarification of the changes in separation performance.

2.1. Cyclone Model

The cyclone separators studied in this research are illustrated in Figure 1 offering a visual depiction of the model utilized in this investigation. The detailed specifications for the geometry of the cyclone separator, which are essential for the experimental setup, are described in Table 1. This table presents the dimensions that show as the basis for the analytical framework.

Fig. 1: (a) A double-stage cyclone Type (b) A lapple cyclone Type³⁴)

Figure 1, shown the double cyclone separator (a) differs from the lapple cyclone (b) in its distinctive structure, the object possesses two lower discharge openings, two entrances, and a central partition. The internal cyclone has identical physical dimensions to the typical lapple cyclone type, except for the variation in the shape of the spiral entry. The outside of the cyclone is of comparable shape as the lapple cyclone separator, but its cylindrical segment with a diameter of 400 mm. Both the outside cyclone and inside cyclone employ a shared vortex detector, each with its own separate hoppers. A baffle is inserted between the outer cyclone and inner cyclone, resulting in the formation of three concentric areas within the double cyclone separator. As a result of the design characteristic, the air containing particles is compelled to create an additional swirling motion within the inner cyclone, allowing the particles to be gathered and collected in two separate hoppers.

Table 1: Geometric descriptions for the cyclone³⁴⁾

The Geometric description	Double-cyclone size	Lapple-cyclone size
Diameter of the Cyclone (Dc)	400 mm	200
Height of the inlet (a)	100 mm	100
Width of the Inlet (b)	50 mm	50 mm
Pipe diameter of the overflow (Do)	100 mm	100 mm
Pipe diameter for the Bottom (Du)	100 mm	50 mm
Length of the cylindrical (Lc)	400 mm	400 mm
Pipe length of the overflow (Lv)	140 mm	140 mm
Length of the cone (Lz)	400 mm	-
Height of the baffle (Lb)	400 mm	-
Diameter of the baffle (Db)	300 mm	-
Cyclone inlet of the inner (c x c)	50 x 50 mm	-
Cyclone diameter of the inner (Dc')	200 mm	-
Cyclone bottom tube diameter of the inner (Du')	50 mm	-
Cyclone cylindrical length of the inner (Lc')	400 mm	-
Cyclone cone length of the inner (Lz')	400 mm	-

2.2. Experimental Data Source and Framework

To evaluate the effectiveness of a novel designed double-stage and lapple cyclone, an experimental setup was designed by experiments conducted by Guoyin Yu et al.³⁴⁾. The velocity input during experiments was adjusted using an inverter to achieve velocities ranging from 12 to 20 m/s. Since the cyclone's entrance area remained constant, changes in speed directly influenced the volume flow rate.

Specifically, the sequence of velocity values was set at 0.06, 0.07, 0.08, 0.09, and flow rate of 0.10 m³/s. Additionally, the concentration of solid feeding was regulated by manipulating the rotation frequency of the feeder, resulting in concentrations of 3.5, 5.0, 6.0, and 9.0 g/m³. Dust particles collected were separated into inner and outer receiving hoppers, while those uncollected were expelled through the airflow.

In the experiment, the dust that was collected is divided into three parts: the input (initial powder), the collection hopper, and the outlet. These parts are quantified as M_{il} , M_h , and M_{ol} , respectively. The total efficiency η_{tot} calculation was conducted according to the method described by Ganegama Bogodage and Leung in 2016³⁵⁾.

$$\eta_{tot} = \frac{M_h}{M_{il}} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

The term "grade efficiency" η_i refers to the ability to separate particles of a specific size or belonging to a limited size region. The total efficiency and grade removal efficiency are related in the following manner:

$$\eta_{tot} = 1 - (1 - \eta_{tot}) \frac{P_{mol}}{P_{mil}} \quad (2)$$

P_{mil} and P_{mol} denote the frequency of mass distribution for particle sizes at the intake and outflow points, respectively, expressed as a percentage. The computation process did not take into account the differences in particle size resulting from particle aggregation and breakage. The separation efficiencies of the outer cyclone separator and the inner in the double-stage cyclone are determined separately as follows:

$$\eta_{tot-o} = \frac{M_{oh}}{M_{il}} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

$$\eta_{tot-i} = \frac{M_{ih}}{M_{ih}+M_{ol}} \times 100\% \quad (4)$$

The outer and also the inner cyclone separator grade efficiency is determined by the following calculation:

$$\eta_{i-o} = \eta_{tot-o} \times \frac{P_{moh}}{P_{mil}} \quad (5)$$

$$\eta_{i-i} = \eta_{tot-i} \times \frac{P_{mih}}{P_{mih}+P_{mol}} \quad (6)$$

The variables η_{tot-o} and η_{tot-i} represent the outer and the inner cyclone total efficiencies. M_{ih} represents the inner hopper mass of particles collected and M_{oh} represents the outer hopper mass of particles collected, respectively. The variable P_{mih} represents the inner hopper particle size as the mass percentages and P_{moh} represents outer hopper particle size as the mass percentages, respectively.

2.3. Optimization Process

The optimization process began with the identification of

key decision variables, namely cyclone diameter, inlet velocity, and particle size, as well as the objective functions, which included total collection efficiency, pressure drop, and grade removal efficiency. The selection of these decision variables was based on their fundamental impact on the aerodynamic behavior and separation performance of cyclone separators. Cyclone diameter influences the residence time and internal flow patterns, thereby affecting the centrifugal forces responsible for particle separation. Inlet velocity is a critical factor that governs the strength of the vortex formation inside the cyclone. While higher inlet velocities can enhance separation efficiency by intensifying centrifugal forces, they also contribute to an increased pressure drop across the system. Meanwhile, particle size plays a direct role in inertial separation mechanisms, larger particles are more readily separated due to their higher inertial response to centrifugal forces. Thus, these three variables are crucial for achieving an optimal trade-off between efficiency, pressure drop, and grade removal performance.

Initially, Response Surface Methodology (RSM) was employed to construct empirical models and conduct a preliminary optimization based on a designed set of experiments. In parallel, Artificial Neural Network (ANN) techniques were applied as a data-driven approach to capture complex nonlinear relationships and improve prediction accuracy. The resulting models from RSM and ANN served as the foundation for conducting multi-objective optimization. The final optimization was carried out using advanced algorithms, specifically the Multi-Objective Genetic Algorithm (MOGA) and the Multi-Objective Ant Lion Optimizer (MOALO), to determine optimal parameter combinations that balance the conflicting objectives effectively.

These optimization methods are used to generate the Pareto front solutions, which represent the set of optimum solutions trade-offs among the objectives. The optimum values obtained are selected from each Pareto front solution using the Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS). This phase guarantees that the chosen values represent the best optimal outcome among the solutions generated by each approach. The findings obtained from the MOGA and MOALO are compared with those from the RSM optimization in order to determine the design factors and objective function that yield the most optimal outcome. This comparison helps in determining the best method for achieving the optimal solutions. The entire optimization process is illustrated in the flowchart shown in Figure 2, Optimization Process.

2.4. Response Surface Methodology (RSM)

Response Surface Methodology (RSM) is a technique used

in Design of Experiment (DoE) to forecast and construct higher order polynomials that represent non-linear correlations between factors and responses³⁶. The DoE outcomes were obtained by utilizing the inputs and replies, establishing a verifiable correlation. In this instance, the results were statistically analysed using RSM in order to obtain improved outcomes. The RSM technique is highly dependable for analysing multiple inputs and outputs in order to get accurate modelling and optimization. In this method, the primary objective is to optimize the surface response, which is influenced by various process parameters³⁷. The RSM design procedure is outlined as follows³⁸:

Planning a series of experiments to ensure feasible and reliable measurements of the response of interest.

Development of a second order response mathematical model with best adjustment.

RSM models aim to fit the data using a second-order polynomial using DesignExpert version 13 software. The responses are visualized either in three-dimensional space or as contour plots. In the second-order model, the response variable Y is described as a linear function of experimental factors, interactions among these factors, quadratic terms, and error terms³⁹:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \sum_{n=1}^k \beta_i X_i + \sum_{n=1}^k \beta_{ii} X_i^2 + \sum_{i < j} \beta_{ij} X_j + \varepsilon \quad (7)$$

Where Y is the response variable, β_0 , β_i , β_{ii} , and β_{ij} are the regression coefficients for constant, linear, quadratic, and interaction, respectively. X_i and X_j are variables independent, and ε is the error. The use of Response Surface Methodology (RSM) improved the establishment of a verifiable linear equation link between the input parameters and their corresponding responses⁴⁰. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) calculated the model's average-squared, squared deviation sums, and degree of freedom for each input value⁴¹. Afterwards, the ANOVA technique was employed to optimize the process by applying the input parameters and assessing the significance of the model based on a linear equation. The 95% confidence level was also utilized to signify the major input value.

The results of experiments utilized for optimizing the double cyclone and lapple cyclone separator through Response Surface Methodology (RSM) are presented in Table 2. This experimental investigation encompasses three factors, which are cyclone diameter, inlet velocity, and particle size. Additionally, it involves three responses include total efficiency, pressure drop, and grade removal efficiency.

Fig 2: Optimization Process

2.5. Artificial Neural Network (ANN)

An Artificial Neural Network (ANN) is a mathematical model designed to mimic the functioning of biological neurons by utilizing parallel processing arrays²³. The training, testing, and validation of the ANN model involved employing a trial-and-error approach to determine an optimal number of neurons and ensure a

more reliable representation of cyclone separator performance.

Fig. 3: Design architecture of ANN

The structure of the neural network layer examined in this study is depicted in Figure 3, a feed-forward Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) architecture was utilized, where the diagram illustrates the input layers, one hidden layer, and output layers in the form of a block diagram, with labelled information flow lines. The ANN based model is

developed with three inputs and three subsequent outputs. The number of hidden neurons in the model varies according to the ANN modelling. This study utilizes the Neural Network Toolbox of MATLAB to examine several feedforward designs in order to enhance the accuracy of predicting cyclone separator performance. The Bayesian regularization algorithm is employed to train the ANN architecture with 1000 epochs and a zero target, following the quasi-Newton principle. Bayesian regularization is a mathematical technique that transforms a nonlinear regression into a statistically well-defined problem, similar to ridge regression. This method offers the benefit of robust models and eliminate the need for the validation procedure, which often grows as $O(N^2)$ in conventional regression methods like back propagation⁴²⁾. The detail summary of the specification of ANN structure used in MATLAB is presented in Table 3.

Table 2: Experimental data of lapple and double cyclone separators by Guoyin Yu et al.³⁴⁾

Type Cyclone	Cyclone Diameter (mm)	Inlet Velocity (m/s)	Particle Size (µm)	Total Efficiency (%)	Pressure Drop (Pa)	Grade Removal Efficiency (%)
Lapple Cyclone	200	12	2.51	52.98	684.51	35.33
	200	14	2.19	56.68	967.37	39.90
	200	16	2.19	58.26	1288.25	40.79
	200	18	2.19	62.49	1591.38	42.19
	200	20	1.91	66.24	1979.85	50.13
Double Cyclone	400	12	2.19	73.74	739.59	62.10
	400	14	2.19	76.56	1009.92	65.96
	400	16	1.68	84.57	1362.66	67.73
	400	18	1.68	82.36	1701.53	70.19
	400	20	1.91	80.42	2100.94	76.02

Table 3: Detail summary specification of ANN structure

Description	Specification
Input layer	3 input layers
Output layer	3 output layers
Hidden Layer	1 hidden layer
Neuron	9 neurons
Training algorithms	Feedforward back propagation
Data division	Random
Training function	Bayesian regularization (trainbr)
Transfer function	Tangent sigmoid transfer function (tansig)
Performance function	Mean squared error (MSE)
Stopping criteria	The training will stop if the maximum number of epochs is reached, or the performance goal is met.

The evaluation of the prediction quality and performance of various ANN models was conducted using established statistical performance indices, such as the mean square

error (MSE). The MSE calculates the average of the squared errors between the measured values of total efficiency, pressure drop, and grade removal efficiency. In the prediction phase, this utilized the Mean Squared Error (MSE) and the coefficient of determination (R^2) parameters in conjunction with ANN to determine the most accurate estimator. The coefficient of correlation R^2 is utilized to quantify the predictive accuracy of the ANN model and demonstrate the extent of variability between the actual measurements of total efficiency, pressure drop, grade removal efficiency, and the predictions made by the ANN model. The Mean Squared Error (MSE) and R-squared (R^2) are computed using the following equation:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - y_i')^2 \tag{8}$$

$$R^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - y_i')^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - y_i'')^2} \tag{9}$$

Where y_i = represent the predicted responses of the ANN model, y_i' = represent the measured efficiency, y_i'' =

represent the average measured efficiency, and n = the number of data samples.

2.6. Multi-objective Optimization Genetic Algorithm (MOGA)

The evolutionary algorithm iteratively adjusts a population of individual solutions, aiming to evolve the present population towards the ideal solution⁴³. The optimization method emulates the natural evolutionary process by creating random combinations of independent variables that represent individuals within a huge population set. The genetic algorithm was employed for conducting multi-objective optimization in order to acquire the pareto solution. The utilization of a multi-objective genetic algorithm encompasses the following stages²⁵:

The refinement of the fitness function following the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) method.

The choice of the initial population.

Establishing the minimum and maximum bound values by empirical inquiry.

Evaluating each individual's fitness function value to determine their rating and selecting the individual with the highest fitness as the parent.

The parent undergoes crossover and mutation to generate a new population.

Iterating the strategy until the outcome satisfies the termination condition. In this instance, the iteration aimed to reach a value of zero for the fitness function in each generation.

These subjects underwent random mutations and emerged as a new population, including their parents, until achieving the best outcome. This cyclic process was self-repetitive. The optimization procedure was conducted using MATLAB's function with a neural function established during the setup of ANN. The Multi-Objective Genetic Algorithm (MOGA) was utilized to enhance the performance of the cyclone separator. In genetic algorithms, a fitness value is essential for solving optimization problems. This fitness value is generated using the RSM and converted into MATLAB files (m-files) within the MATLAB software. In this optimization analysis, constraints for each variable were defined, and parameters were adjusted until the function was ready for operation. By employing MOGA, the results produced optimal solutions in Pareto, allowing for trade-offs to be assessed to meet various objectives.

2.7. Multi-objective Ant Lion Optimizer (MOALO)

MOALO is an extension of ALO for solving multi-objective optimization problems through two additional operations such as employing an archive to store the Pareto solution, and using the leader selection and archive maintenance mechanism³³. The optimization process was implemented using MATLAB. This approach was utilized

for both the Design of Experiment (DoE) and Artificial Neural Network (ANN) applications. The complete procedure of MOALO can be succinctly outlined as follows³³:

The process of setting up initial populations for ants and antlions, as well as determining the size of the archive.

Assessment of the objective roles of ants and antlions.

Commence the process of iteration. Using the roulette wheel approach, choose the antlion and elite from the archive for each ant.

Modifying the radius of ants' random walk, normalizing, and verifying the boundary

Implementing the elitism technique to update the position of the ants.

Following the previous two steps, compute the fitness of all ants.

Please ensure that the archive is updated and verify its current condition.

At the conclusion of the iteration, the archive should be outputted.

By employing MOALO, the results produced optimal solutions in the Pareto front. This allowed for the assessment of trade-offs to meet various objectives. MOALO helped identify the best solutions by considering different competing factors, making decision-making more effective for the cyclone separator performance.

2.8. Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS)

Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) founded on the fundamental principle that the optimal solution is characterized by the minimum distance from the positive-ideal solution and the maximum distance from the negative-ideal solution. The alternatives are ranked by calculating an overall index that takes into account the distances from the optimal answers⁴⁴.

The TOPSIS method is employed to determine the most optimum value of cyclone separator produced by both MOGA and MOALO from both the Design of Experiment (DoE) and Artificial Neural Network (ANN) models. TOPSIS was conducted using MATLAB software to ascertain the most optimal value through a series of steps. Firstly, criteria values are transformed into a comparable scale via normalization. Then, the normalized decision matrix is multiplied by the weights of each criterion to derive the weighted normalized matrix. Following this, the weighted normalized matrix is used to determine the optimal (positive ideal) and suboptimal (negative ideal) values for each criterion. Afterwards, the Euclidean distance is calculated to determine the distance of each alternative from both the positive ideal solution and the negative ideal solution. Subsequently, the proximity of each alternative to the optimal solution is assessed. Ultimately, the options are evaluated and rated according to their proximity to the ideal answer, with the highest

proximity signifying the most optimal choice.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. RSM Model Development and Analysis

The RSM optimization utilizes secondary data from Table 2. The data is loaded into Design Expert version 13 software, which utilizes custom designs to model the experiment. The values of both factors and responses were obtained using secondary data. The historical mode is selected for designing, based on an existing dataset, to perform predictive modelling and subsequently optimize it. The fit statistics data presented in Table 4. indicate a slightly improved outcome, as evaluated by the R2 value, when employing the optimal lambda value determined from the result of fit statistics. Subsequently, the investigation proceeds by utilizing linear process order for the total efficiency, grade removal efficiency, and pressure drop respectively. A higher R2 indicates that a greater proportion of the variations observed in the dependent variable can be accounted by the independent variable. The modified version also demonstrates a higher level of precision in both responses, indicating a greater accuracy in the estimation derived from a statistical model or analysis. It indicates that the results are accurate enough to make significant inferences.

A correlation was derived empirically from the data obtained through the Design of Experiments (DoE) for the factors and responses. This was complemented by the statistical analysis using RSM to generate the predicted result. Moreover, the different outcomes of the three reactions, specifically total efficiency, pressure drop, and grade removal efficiency, were detected by alterations in the cyclone diameter, velocity, and particle size. Table 5. displays the percentages obtained by the utilization of Design of Experiment (DoE) using Design Expert software for the input parameters to show the actual and predicted results.

Table 4: Fit statistics for total efficiency, pressure drop, and grade removal efficiency

Source	Total Efficiency (%)	Pressure Drop (Pa)	Grade removal efficiency (%)
Std. Dev	1.79	39.20	1.76
Mean	69.43	1342.60	55.03
C.V. %	2.58	2.92	3.20
R ²	0.9841	0.9959	0.9907
Adjusted R ²	0.9761	0.9938	0.9861
Predicted R ²	0.9469	0.9856	0.9751
Adequate Precision	27.2375	57.0482	35.5615

The analysis of variance, as shown in Table 6, reveals the ways in which the input, sum of squares, and their interactions contribute to the analysis of the output. Furthermore, it revealed that the observed traits were essential in assessing the produced model. Table 6 shows that the developed model has an F-value of 123.39 for Total efficiency elimination, with a P-value of less than 0.05. This demonstrates that the model terms with P-values below 0.05 were statistically significant, suggesting the validity of the adopted experimental conditions. The analysis of variance table revealed that the treatment cyclone diameter had the greatest impact on the overall efficiency. The total efficiency model was derived by utilizing Equation (10). Based on these findings, the equation plays a crucial role in highlighting the several factors that impact the overall efficiency. The variables A, B, and C were used to represent the cyclone diameter, inlet velocity, and particle size, respectively, in this investigation.

Table 6 presents the analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the pressure drop results. The F-value and P-value were observed to be 480.35 and less than 0.05, respectively. The results demonstrated that the variable exerting the most notable influence on pressure drop was found to be the inlet velocity. The F-value of 480.35 indicates that the model is statistically significant. Equation (11) represents the created system for estimating pressure drop.

$$\text{Total Efficiency} = 69.03 + 8.36A + 2.20B - 5.40C \quad (10)$$

$$\text{Pressure Drop} = 1344.59 + 48.94A + 677.49B - 26.68C \quad (11)$$

Table 6 also displays the ANOVA analysis results for grade removal efficiency, showing an observed F-value of 213.79 and a P-value of less than 0.05. This suggests that the cyclone diameter is the most influential variable for the P-value is <0.0001 indicating a high level of significance for the model. Furthermore, Equation (12) served as the formulated model for estimating the grade removal efficiency.

$$\text{Grade Removal Efficiency} = 55.06 + 13.48A + 6.59B - 0.3555C \quad (12)$$

The normality of residuals can be assessed by examining the normal probability plot, which should display a straight line if the residuals follow a normal distribution. Figure 4, displays the total efficiency ranging from 52.98% to 84.57%, the pressure drops ranging from 684.51 to 2100.94 Pa, and the grade removal efficiency ranging from 35.33 to 76.02%. There are outliers in the data that will be further examined in the following diagnosis.

Table 5: Result of DoE actual and predicted results

Type Cyclone	Cyclone Diameter (mm)	Inlet Velocity (m/s)	Particle Size (μm)	Actual Total Efficiency (%)	Predicted Total Efficiency (%)	Actual Pressure Drop (Pa)	Predicted Pressure Drop (Pa)	Actual Grade Removal Efficiency (%)	Predicted Grade Removal Efficiency (%)
Lapple Cyclone	200	12	2.51	52.98	53.08	684.51	644.84	35.33	35.34
	200	14	2.19	56.68	58.34	967.37	963.01	39.90	38.37
	200	16	2.19	58.26	59.43	1288.25	1301.76	40.79	41.66
	200	18	2.19	62.49	60.53	1591.38	1640.50	42.19	44.96
	200	20	1.91	66.24	65.27	1979.85	1961.25	50.13	48.01
Double Cyclone	400	12	2.19	73.74	73.95	739.59	722.15	62.10	62.03
	400	14	2.19	76.56	75.05	1009.92	1060.90	65.96	65.33
	400	16	1.68	84.57	82.78	1362.66	1366.86	67.73	68.19
	400	18	1.68	82.36	83.88	1701.53	1705.60	70.19	71.48
	400	20	1.91	80.42	81.99	2100.94	2059.13	76.02	74.97

Table 6: Analysis of variance for total efficiency, pressure drop, and grade removal efficiency

Response	Process Order	Source	Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	P-value
Total efficiency	Linear	Model	1183.69	3	394.56	123.39	<0.0001
		A: Cyclone diameter	352.95	1	352.95	110.38	<0.0001
		B: Inlet velocity	10.04	1	10.04	3.14	0.1268
		C: Particle size	31.02	1	31.02	9.70	0.0207
		Residual	19.19	6	3.20		
		Cor total	1202.87	9			
Pressure drop	Linear	Model	2.214E+05	3	7.381E+05	480.35	<0.0001
		A: Cyclone diameter	12104.54	1	12104.54	7.88	0.0309
		B: Inlet velocity	9.544E+05	1	9.544E+05	621.16	<0.0001
		C: Particle size	758.06	1	758.06	0.4934	0.5088
		Residual	9219.14	6	1536.52		
		Cor total	2.223E+06	9			
Grade removal efficiency	Linear	Model	1991.18	3	663.73	213.79	<0.0001
		A: Cyclone diameter	918.36	1	918.36	295.81	<0.0001
		B: Inlet velocity	90.32	1	90.32	29.09	0.0017
		C: Particle size	0.1346	1	0.1346	0.0434	0.8419
		Residual	18.63	6	3.10		
		Cor total	2009.81	9			

The normality of residuals can be assessed by examining the normal probability plot, which should display a straight line if the residuals follow a normal distribution. Figure 4 displays the total efficiency ranging from 52.98% to 84.57%, the pressure drops ranging from 684.51 to 2100.94 Pa, and the grade removal efficiency ranging from 35.33 to 76.02%. There are outliers in the data that will be further examined in the following diagnosis.

The plot in Figure 5, displays the diagnostic for the predicted, actual, residual, and run, providing a thorough assessment of a predictive model's performance in terms of total efficiency, pressure drop, and grade removal efficiency. It is comparing the predicted values to the actual values shows a strong correlation along the diagonal,

suggesting that the model's predictions closely correspond to the observed values, thereby displaying its high level of accuracy. The absence of a noticeable pattern in the Residual vs. Predicted plot indicates that the predictions are impartial and fair across the whole range of data. It evaluates the hypothesis of uniform variance. The plot is exhibiting a random dispersion, with a consistent range of residuals throughout the graph.

Similarly, the Residual vs. Run plot does not display any discernible trend across several observations, suggesting that the errors of the model are not influenced by the order of the observations, thereby ensuring consistent performance. The residuals versus experimental run-order plot are used to identify any latent variables that may have

affected the response during the experiment. The plot shows a random scatter of residuals against the experimental run order. Figure 5 demonstrates the correctness, fairness, and consistency of the predictive model, which increases trust in its reliable capacity to anticipate total efficiency, pressure drop, and grade removal efficiency.

To understand how factors influence the results, regression models can be utilized to produce diverse 2D contour and 3D response surface plots for any combination of the factors. These plots are generated by systematically adjusting all potential combinations of components within the experimental range, while keeping the remaining factors constant at their central value²⁷⁾.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 4: Normal plot for (a) Total efficiency (b) Pressure drop (c) Grade removal efficiency

Figure 6 (a) depicts 2D contour and 3D response surface plots showcasing total of the efficiency. The plots depicting response surfaces in both 2D, and 3D display comparable patterns for the three pairings of factors. The total efficiency increased as the inlet velocity and cyclone diameter were raised within the experimental range. Based on the contour plots, it was seen that the overall efficiency increased as the particle size decreased. Figure 6 (b) illustrates the impact of the three parameters on reducing the pressure drop as the inlet velocity drops. The diameter of the cyclone has a minimal impact on the pressure drop, provided the iso-lines remain perfectly straight. It has been observed that when the value of the inlet velocity is increased, there is an initial quick increase in the pressure drop. Moreover, when comparing different factors, reducing the inlet velocity, cyclone diameter, and particle size is a significantly more effective method for reducing the pressure drop, albeit with a slight fall in total efficiency. Furthermore, Figure 6 (c) illustrates the impact of the three parameters on the enhanced the grade removal as the cyclone diameter and inlet velocity increase. The particle size does not have a substantial impact on the grade removal efficiency. However, increasing the particle size does result in a slight improvement in the grade removal efficiency. Ultimately, maximizing the optimization of grade removal efficiency can be achieved by increasing the cyclone diameter, intake velocity, and particle size. This decision will result in an increased pressure drop and a slight decrease in total efficiency.

Fig. 5: Diagnostic of residual, actual, predicted, and run (a) Total efficiency (b) Pressure drop (c) Grade removal efficiency

Fig. 6: The contour surface 2D and 3D plots by RSM for (a) Total efficiency (b) Pressure drop (c) Grade removal efficiency

3.2. RSM Optimization

After establishing the mathematical model, optimization techniques are utilized to determine the most favourable conditions for the system. The objective is to identify the optimal combination of input elements that either maximizes or minimize the desired responses. The process of numerical optimization was conducted using the same software by specifying the range of all parameters'

boundaries. The optimization criteria, as indicated in Table 7. were applied across the entire range due to a lack of sufficient data. Through a process of experimentation and learning from mistakes, it is evident that this spectrum of solutions consistently receives a high grade in terms of desirability. Furthermore, the weight is uniformly assigned to all parameters, suggesting that the factors and replies hold equal significance. The weight is 1, and the

importance value is 3. The solutions obtained from the three-variable optimization process are depicted in Figure 7. Selected solutions, which exhibit high desirability. This indicates that optimal performance is achieved by utilizing the lower end of the inlet velocity range, the lower limit for particle size, and the upper limit for cyclone diameter, specifically the double cyclone type. The findings uncovered substantial difficulties in applying optimization

for lapple and double cyclone separators. The objective of this procedure is to significantly enhance the performance of the cyclone separator by employing Response Surface Methodology (RSM). The ramp functions of the ideal solutions yielded significant improvements, increasing the values of the total efficiency, pressure drop, and grade removal efficiency.

Fig. 7: Ramps of RSM Optimization

Figure 8, provides a vivid depiction of a 2D contour plot that demonstrates the impact of varying these factors on the percentage of total efficiency, grade removal efficiency, and pressure drop. Increasing or decreasing these variables leads to a significant increase in overall efficiency and grade removal efficiency, while simultaneously reducing the pressure drop. However, the impact of particle size on improving the total reaction was minimal. This implies that while particle size does have an impact on the cyclone separator, its influence on the overall outcome of the samples is unlikely to be significant when compared to factors such as cyclone diameter and inlet velocity. The performance optimization process resulted in the selection of a cyclone separator with a desirability of 0.825. The selected cyclone diameter is 400 mm, the velocity at the inlet is 12 m/s, and the particle size is 1.68 μm . As a result, the total efficiency is 80.58%, the pressure drop is 689.71 Pa, and the grade removal efficiency is 61.59%. The results demonstrate a noteworthy association between the cyclone's diameter, the inlet velocity, and the efficiency of removing particles of a certain grade.

Fig 8: Contour of RSM Solution for (a) desirability, (b) total efficiency, (c) pressure drop, and (d) grade removal efficiency

Table 7: Criteria of RSM optimization

Variables	Setup Goal	Lower Limit Value	Upper Limit Value
Cyclone diameter (mm)	In range	200	400
Inlet velocity (m/s)	In range	12	20
Particle size (μm)	In range	1.68	2.51
Total efficiency (%)	Maximize	52.98	84.57
Pressure drop (Pa)	Minimize	684.51	2100.94
Grade removal efficiency (%)	Maximize	35.33	76.02

3.3. ANN Training and Modelling Optimization

ANN analysis, like RSM modelling, is employed to establish the correlation between the three input variables and the three output variables. The analysis involves several processes, such as data collection, network building and configuration, weight and bias initialization,

training, testing, and validation. The optimal regression value (R) that minimizes the mean squared error (MSE) is also predicted to be achieved with the suitably selected neurons. The ANN model employed in this study comprised of 3 input variables, 1 hidden layer containing 9 neurons, and 3 target output variables.

The optimal design was determined using a trial-and-error process, along with the selection of the architecture that had the lowest error (RMSE) and the best regression coefficient. Figure 2 provided an observation of the architecture of the artificial neural network. The network error level, sometimes referred to as the difference between the model's output and the intended data, is a key aspect of this process. The backpropagation method facilitated the acquisition of fresh information during the testing phase by calculating the optimal weights for attainment at the highest point. In this instance, the weights were iteratively adjusted in order to minimize errors during training. This suggests that the implementation of reverse computing approach led to a substantial reduction in the error value.

The high coefficient of determination (R) in the regression analysis indicates a strong correlation between the variables, resulting in a more precise trendline. Based on Figure 9, the blue line representing the training state exhibited the most precise trendline, intersecting every point on the graph. The R-value for this trendline was 0.99. The regression coefficient (R) values for the trendlines in the training, testing, and overall were all 0.99, as shown in Figure 9 (a). This involved calculating multiple correlation coefficients and making comparisons between the regression model and ANN (Artificial Neural Network) both during the training phase and the testing phase. Figure 9 (b-d) also displayed the error histogram, together with the training performance and state. In this case, the error histogram refers to the discrepancy between the goal values and the predicted values obtained from the feedforward neural network after it has undergone training. The error values further elucidate the distinct patterns of the anticipated and desired rates, as depicted by the performance graph showcasing the network's optimal validation efficiency. The training process automatically terminates when the mean squared error (MSE) of the validation samples increases.

Fig. 9: (a) Regression data of ANN (b) error histogram (c) best training performance (d) state of the training

Figure 10, shows the correlation plot between the actual data, RSM, and ANN prediction result. When predicting the total efficiency, both ANN and RSM exhibited trends that nearly matched the observed values. This suggests that both methods offer dependable models for predicting grade removal efficiency. The Artificial Neural Network demonstrated superior accuracy compared to the RSM in predicting total efficiency and pressure drop. The performance of ANN in predicting the total efficiency and pressure drop can be attributed to the remarkable regression findings, which achieved an R2 value of 0.99. The high R2 value indicates that ANN model successfully captured and reproduced the fundamental connections within the data, resulting in highly reliable predictions. The fluctuation in the gradient coefficient is also noticed in relation to the training state, which is influenced by the number of epochs. This demonstrated that every output prediction data exhibited a regression value that was in close proximity to 1, specifically 0.99. To forecast the overall efficiency, pressure decrease, and targeted data for grade removal efficiency. The performance map in Figure 9(c) shows that the training process was halted at 0.057823 within epoch 231, which falls within the authorized range.

Fig. 10: ANN and RSM versus actual values of (a) total efficiency, (b) pressure drop, (c) grade removal efficiency

3.4. MOGA and MOALO Optimization

MOGA and MOALO analysis was conducted using MATLAB software to generate Pareto graphs for the three objective functions including total efficiency, pressure drop, and grade removal efficiency of the cyclone separator. The optimization process was conducted using the estimates derived from the Design of Experiments (DoE), specifically equations (10)-(12). The aims of achieving maximum overall efficiency and grade removal efficiency values were pursued, while simultaneously minimizing the pressure drop value, in order to achieve optimal performance of the cyclone separator. Furthermore, the input range values for the diameter of the cyclone, the velocity at the inlet, and the size of the particles were established based on the prior experimental data. MOGA and MOALO analysis are also done using the estimation results from ANN. The constructed network function exhibited high precision in forecasting the values of total efficiency, pressure drop, and grade removal efficiency. The function derived from the ANN process was subsequently utilized as a fitness criterion during the optimization phase, based on the obtained results. In order to choose the population and optimize the operations.

Figure 11 presents a pareto front comparison of MOGA RSM, MOGA ANN, MOALO RSM, and MOALO ANN for each output variable, including (a) total efficiency vs. pressure drop, (b) grade removal efficiency vs. pressure drops, and (c) total efficiency vs. grade removal efficiency. In Figure 11 (a) and 11(b), the distribution pattern remains within range. However, in Figure 11 (c), there is a significant difference in the minimum values of grade removal efficiency between the DoE and ANN using MOGA and MOALO optimization. This Figure illustrates the distribution of optimal results from each method used in this study. The optimization achieved using the Design of Experiments (DoE) equation is reflected in the results for MOGA RSM and MOALO RSM. The Pareto graph indicates that the highest ideal values for total efficiency, pressure drop, and grade removal efficiency of the cyclone separator were 84.56%, 2064.37 Pa, and 74.45% for MOGA RSM, respectively, and 83.95%, 2049.77 Pa, and 75.51% for MOALO RSM, respectively. The minimum values for these parameters for MOGA RSM were 61.60%, 591.39 Pa, and 34.46%, while for MOALO RSM, they were 64.35%, 594.88 Pa, and 35.42%. In this context, the highest values obtained by the MOGA technique closely matched the range achieved through DoE optimization using both the MOGA and MOALO methods.

Fig. 11: Pareto Front Comparison of MOGA RSM, MOGA ANN, MOALO RSM, and MOALO ANN (a) pressure drop vs total efficiency (b) pressure drop vs grade removal efficiency, (c) total efficiency vs grade removal efficiency

In Figure 11, the Pareto front solutions were also obtained by applying the Bayesian regularization method to solve the optimization model for ANN. The optimization using the MOGA ANN-based prediction equation yielded maximum ideal values of 83.99% for total efficiency, 2113.36 Pa for pressure drop, and 75.74% for grade removal efficiency. The MOALO ANN-based optimization yielded maximum ideal values of 83.22% for overall efficiency, 2103.58 Pa for pressure drop, and 74.90% for grade removal efficiency. The minimum values obtained were 64.65% for total efficiency, 623.20 Pa for pressure drop, and 52.00% for grade removal efficiency for MOGA ANN. For MOALO ANN, the minimum values obtained were 64.91% for total efficiency, 620.03 Pa for pressure drop, and 52.42% for grade removal efficiency. Thus, the output ranges of the optimization processes based on ANN and DoE were comparable.

The optimal value was obtained using the TOPSIS method in MATLAB software for MOGA and MOALO methods,

and Design Expert software for the Response Surface Methodology (RSM) optimization. Therefore, these findings allow for the identification of the most favourable value for each optimization technique. Figure 11, provides 3D plot comparative analysis of five optimization and prediction models of MOGA RSM, MOGA ANN, MOALO RSM, MOALO ANN, and RSM optimization of the cyclone separator. The MOGA RSM model, represented by red spheres, shows an optimal point with approximately 60.5% grade removal efficiency, a pressure drop of 719.09 Pa, and a total efficiency of 78.5%. This model demonstrates moderate grade removal efficiency with relatively high total efficiency, indicating a balanced performance. On the other hand, the MOGA ANN model, represented by blue spheres, achieves a superior grade removal efficiency of around 65.21% with a pressure drop of 746.37 Pa and an overall efficiency of 74.60%. This model exhibits a commendable overall efficiency while marginally increasing the pressure drop, rendering it a feasible choice for applications that demand enhanced efficiency.

Fig. 12: 3D plot MOGA RSM, MOGA ANN, MOALO RSM, MOALO ANN, and RSM optimization

Figure 12, shows the MOALO RSM model that represented by magenta spheres, achieving an optimum result with a grade removal efficiency of 61.67%, a pressure drop of 719.75 Pa, and an overall efficiency of 74.17%. It shows similar performance to MOGA RSM in terms of pressure drop and grade removal efficiency, while displaying moderate overall efficiency. The MOALO ANN model, shown by green spheres, achieves a peak grade removal efficiency of approximately 66.15%, accompanied by a pressure drop of 761.11 Pa and an overall efficiency of 76.02%. This model achieves maximum efficiency but requires a higher pressure drop, which means there is a trade-off between efficiency and pressure requirements. The RSM Optimization method is denoted by green stars, which indicate the maximum total efficiency of 80.58%, comparatively low pressure

decreases of 689.37 Pa, and a moderate grade removal efficiency of 61.59%. The MOGA ANN and MOALO ANN models provide superior removal and overall efficiency, albeit with the drawback of increased pressure drop. Meanwhile, the MOGA RSM and MOALO RSM

models offer reduced pressure drops while maintaining modest efficiency. The RSM optimization exhibits superior total efficiency, minimal pressure drops, and a modest level of grade removal efficiency.

Table 8: Optimal Result Optimization

Optimization Method	Cyclone Diameter (mm)	Inlet Velocity (m/s)	Particle Size (μm)	Total Efficiency (%)	Pressure Drop (Pa)	Grade Removal Efficiency (%)
MOGA RSM	391.70	12.16	1.77	78.5	719.09	60.50
MOGA ANN	396.12	12.07	2.12	74.59	746.37	65.21
MOALO RSM	400	12	2.15	74.17	719.75	61.67
MOALO ANN	400	12	2.03	76.02	761.11	66.15
RSM Optimization	400	12	1.68	80.58	689.37	61.59

Table 8 shows the outcomes of each optimization technique. The optimal result optimization section showcases the results obtained from several optimization techniques used to a certain process. It specifically examines aspects such as cyclone diameter, inlet velocity, and particle size, as well as response variables such as overall efficiency, pressure drop, and grade removal efficiency. The RSM Optimization method yielded the highest overall efficiency of 80.58%, the lowest pressure drop of 689.37 Pa, and a moderate grade removal efficiency of 61.59%. These results were obtained using a cyclone diameter of 400 mm, an inlet velocity of 12 m/s, and a particle size of 1.68 μm . Therefore, the RSM Optimization method is deemed the most optimal for the cyclone separator. The parameter values fall within the range specified in Table 2. The experimental data verifies that the cyclone being used is a double cyclone separator. Table 8. presents a clear comparison of the result of each optimization approach. It is evident that RSM Optimization outperforms the others and shows the highest overall performance for the cyclone separator.

3.5. Effect of Decision Variables on Optimization Objectives

Understanding how each decision variable influences the objective functions is essential for interpreting the optimization results and ensuring the physical validity of the model. In this study, cyclone diameter was shown to be a dominant factor affecting both total efficiency and grade removal efficiency. Physically, a larger diameter increases the chamber volume, allowing longer residence time and enabling more particles to settle out before escaping. This leads to enhanced collection efficiency, particularly for fine particles, and is supported by high positive coefficients in the RSM regression models. The ANOVA results further confirmed its significance, showing the

highest F-value for cyclone diameter in total and grade efficiency models. The optimal diameter consistently identified across all optimization approaches was 400 mm, the upper limit of the tested range indicating that maximum separation is achieved under this geometric configuration, especially in the double-stage design.

Inlet velocity plays a dual role in cyclone separator performance. On one hand, increasing the velocity enhances the centrifugal force acting on the particles, improving both total and grade removal efficiency. On the other hand, it significantly increases pressure drop, resulting in higher energy consumption. This trade-off was clearly captured in the regression model, where inlet velocity had the largest positive coefficient for pressure drop and was the most significant factor in the ANOVA with an F-value exceeding 600. While higher velocities improve separation, they come at the cost of energy efficiency. Therefore, in multi-objective optimization, a balance must be struck. The optimal inlet velocity determined through all optimization methods was 12 m/s, the lowest value tested, which maintained high efficiency while minimizing pressure loss.

Particle size affects the ease with which particles are separated from the gas stream. Smaller particles have lower inertia and are more likely to follow airflow lines, reducing the collection rate. This is reflected in the negative coefficient for particle size in the total efficiency model. However, the influence of particle size on grade removal efficiency was minimal, as shown by its small regression coefficient and statistically insignificant P-value in the ANOVA result. Moreover, particle size had negligible effect on pressure drop, since it does not directly alter flow resistance. Despite its limited statistical significance, optimization results consistently favored the smallest tested particle size of 1.68 μm , which aligns with the goal of designing systems that efficiently handle fine

particulate matter.

Overall, this study demonstrates that cyclone diameter, inlet velocity, and particle size are not only appropriate and scientifically grounded choices for optimization but also exhibit predictable and interpretable effects on performance. The combined use of RSM, ANN, MOGA, and MOALO validated these relationships and enabled the identification of optimal configurations that balance performance and efficiency for both single and double-stage cyclone separators.

4. Conclusion

The study utilized data-driven methods such as Response Surface Methodology (RSM), Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Multi-objective Genetic Algorithm (MOGA), and a novel approach, Multi-objective Ant Lion Optimizer (MOALO), to predict and optimize the performance of the double and lapple cyclone separator. This shed light on the complexities associated with experimentally determining the most effective cyclone diameter, inlet velocity, and particle size, highlighting the vital role of the machine learning methods employed. The integration of RSM and ANN produced highly precise models, as evidenced by R2 values exceeding 0.95, which confirms the model's high predictive accuracy.

Furthermore, MOGA, MOALO, and RSM optimization unveiled the precise parameters for achieving the optimum values of a double cyclone outperforms a lapple cyclone in terms of cyclone performance. According to the multi-objectives technique, using a cyclone with a diameter of 400 mm, the velocity at the inlet is 12 m/s, and particles with a size of 1.68 μm would result in a total efficiency of 80.58%, a pressure drop of 689.71 Pa, and grade removal efficiency of 61.59%.

This research effectively utilized Response Surface Methodology (RSM), Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Multi objective Genetic Algorithm (MOGA) and a novel approach Multi-objective Ant Lion Optimizer (MOALO) to demonstrate its suitability for the specific scenario of a lapple and double cyclone in the context of cyclone separators. The results underscore the model's precision and effectiveness in enhancing the system's performance.

Although this study primarily relies on computational modeling and secondary experimental data, the optimization results are grounded in experimentally validated findings from existing literature. Nonetheless, we acknowledge the necessity of experimental validation to confirm the effectiveness and practical applicability of the proposed optimization strategies. Future research should prioritize physical testing based on the identified optimal configurations to strengthen the real-world relevance of the outcomes.

It is also important to note that this study does not include a comprehensive uncertainty analysis. In subsequent work,

incorporating methods such as Monte Carlo simulations or global sensitivity analysis is recommended to assess the influence of parameter uncertainties on cyclone performance. Such analyses would offer valuable insights into the robustness and reliability of the optimized designs under varying operating conditions. To further enhance the reliability of this optimization framework, future studies should generate new datasets through experimental validation. Additionally, randomized trials should be conducted to minimize bias and support the generalizability of the findings.

Acknowledgment

This work was supported by the Hibah Publikasi Terindeks Internasional (PUTI) Q1 from Directorates of Research and Development Universitas Indonesia to Nasruddin [grant number NKB-535/UN2.RST/HKP.05.00/2023]. The corresponding author would like to express gratitude to Directorate General of Higher Education, Research, and Technology (DIKTI), Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology, Republic of Indonesia which provided the opportunity to finalize this article during his participation in SAME 2023 Grant Program at ETH Zurich.

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